

THE IMPACT FAMILIAL ROLES HAS ON LATINX COLLEGE STUDENTS'
MENTAL HEALTH

by

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Abstract

This study aims to investigate how family roles directly affect Latinx college students' mental well-being. Specifically, I examine how to best support Latinx students as they pursue higher education by exploring (1) what family roles these students engage in and (2) how family roles impact their mental health. These questions brought forth two hypotheses: Latinx college students (1) will provide more emotional support to their families than they receive, which would negatively affect their mental health, and (2) will have a harder time maintaining their family roles during their college years. I took a qualitative approach to investigating these questions by conducting three semi-structured interviews with college students. Interviews were transcribed and thematic codes were assigned leading to five family roles being identified, with the mediator role being a new responsibility not mentioned in previous literature. The first hypothesis was supported suggesting that Latinx college students do take on more roles. However, not all students viewed these roles negatively. Two students mentioned the pressure and anxiety they felt to maintain their family roles and navigate school life, while another expressed the freedom college granted them. My second hypothesis was also partially supported since two students reported difficulty balancing their home and school responsibilities while another expressed the independence they gained since starting college.

Keywords: family roles, immigration, mental health, Latinx, college students

The Impact Familial Roles Has on Latinx College Students' Mental Health

Many colleges and universities are responding to students' desires to attend more diverse, equitable, and inclusive learning environments that are also more receptive to student mental health. Adapting an inclusive educational approach by respecting a variety of student backgrounds requires universities to create educational spaces that promote learning, well-being, retention, and positive mental health (Lipson et al., 2018). With an ever-growing ethnically and racially diverse U.S. college population, much research has aimed to understand the life experiences and perceptions of students of color.

College students of color often report experiencing poor racial climate, anxiety, lack of support from faculty, low sense of belonging, and difficulty adapting to increased academic expectations throughout their academic endeavors (Morgan et al., 2020). Not much attention, however, has been dedicated to understanding the unique experiences and needs of immigrant college students of color. In addition to the challenges of being a college student of color, immigrant students often face the added stress of needing to learn how to navigate cultural differences and daily interactions in a country that is foreign to themselves and their parents (George et al., 2019; Yoon et al., 2017). First-generation students are also more likely than their non-first-generation peers to experience stress and anxiety from potentially needing to learn a new language, providing physical or financial support, or assuming extra familial responsibilities not commonly expected of college students (Covarrubias et al., 2019). Throughout their college journey, these factors may negatively impact their mental health. So, if universities are truly aiming for inclusivity and providing better mental health resources for students, then students with immigrant parents or caregivers and immigrant students of color need to be a part of this conversation.

According to the U.S. Department of Commerce Census Bureau (2019), more students of color are enrolling in four-year institutions with a 31% enrollment rate. Among those students, the U.S. Department of Commerce Census Bureau (2019) notes that Black college students experienced an increase of 6%, while Hispanic college students encountered a surge in enrollment rates up to 14% between 2000 and 2018. In comparison, Asian students had the highest admission in 2018 with 59% (U.S. Census Bureau, 2019). However, despite the growth in college admittance among these ethnic groups, they also have high rates of mental health issues. Lipson et al. (2018) found that 51% of Asian students and 62% of African American students met the criteria for one or more mental health problems. As for Latino students, about 65% suffer from deteriorating mental health and go without treatment (Warren, 2021). Among these ethnic minorities, research supports that immigrant students from the Latinx, Black, and Asian communities are overall less likely than their non-immigrant peers to utilize mental health services (Derr, 2016) with Latinx students experiencing more issues due to conflicting cultural values causing mental health concerns (Arevalo et al, 2016; Covarrubias et al., 2019; Vasquez-Salgado et al., 2015). Specifically, Latinx students encounter difficulty with labeling their specific symptoms (De Silva et al., 2020) and navigating their demanding family-school life (Vasquez-Salgado et al., 2015) often leading them to internalize their emotions (Galvan & Gudiño, 2019).

Scholars speculate that students from Latinx communities' susceptibility to experience distress lies within cultural differences such as coming from a more collectivist culture, which puts an emphasis on caring for others' needs before their own (Covarrubias et al., 2019; Vasquez-Salgado et al., 2015). From these perspectives, Latinx students may feel guilty when debating whether to uphold their school or family responsibilities (Vasquez-Salgado et al., 2015)

or feel obligated to give back to their families for supporting them through college (Trieu 2016). Perhaps it's the need to abide by their culture's norms or the difficulty in navigating their identity that deter these students from using mental health resources (Vasquez-Salgado et al., 2015; Yoon, 2017). But, mental health services on campus provide additional support that these students could use to excel in school (George, 2020; Johnson-Esparza et al., 2021; Katsiaticas et al., 2019).

In view of this, the purpose of this study is to determine how to best support Latinx students as they pursue a higher education by exploring (1) what family roles these students engage in and (2) how family roles impact their mental health. In the following literature review, studies that detail the implications familial upbringing and culture have on the mental health of students from the Latinx community will be discussed.

Review of Literature

Latinx Mental Health

The following section explores how Latinx children learn to perceive mental health and mental health services, including how their perceptions impact their mental health. Literature that investigates other factors that hinder or directly impact Latinx college student's mental health, such as collectivism, family roles, and the American Dream, will also be discussed in this section.

Seeking mental health support is a learned behavior. Youth often depend on their parents to teach them how to recognize and respond to mental health symptoms. For instance, Latinx parents disclose the difficulty in distinguishing between depressive and anxiety symptoms as one main component in the low usage rates of psychological services (De Silva et al., 2020). Rather than describing their symptoms from a psychological perspective, the Latinx community focuses

on the physical attributes, such as children appearing sad (*triste*) or nervous (*ansioso*) (De Silva et al., 2020). So, rather than discerning signs of internal struggle, parents perceive this as a physical issue due to their poor knowledge of mental health. This could lead to youth internalizing their needs; meaning these children will not vocally express their struggles, leading them to keep these concerns to themselves and go without help. Unfortunately, youth with "internalizing needs are less likely to receive...mental health services" (Galvan & Gudiño, 2019, p. 4). Children who internalize their symptoms depend on their parents to recognize their inner psychological conflict, but parent reports of not being fully aware of mental health issues leaves children to suffer in silence (De Silva et al., 2020).

Another common obstacle is the stigmatization of mental health, which prevents parents from reaching out for professional help for their children (De Silva et al., 2020). Latinx parents prefer to look for support within their respective communities rather than seeking professional help to avoid feelings of shame (De Silva et al., 2020). So, instead of acknowledging the help their children need, parents may feel socially pressured to only recognize anxiety and depression as not real problems (De Silva et al., 2020). Ultimately, this leaves about 23.25% of youth to develop internalized needs (Galvan & Gudiño, 2019). Without the proper education on mental health issues, this percentage will continue to grow, therefore increasing Latinx disparity in treatment outreach.

On top of the existing stigma, collectivism (group over self) can also function as a stressor for Latinx children. Collectivism helps maintain family cohesion and structure, which appears through everyday family interactions. For instance, to preserve family dynamics, each family member assumes one or multiple roles. Children commonly act as a language broker among their immigrant families where they translate for their parents as one of their family roles

(Covarrubias et al., 2019). These various roles can manifest and change at any given age, but failure to adhere to their roles can cause family tension.

In addition to cultural perceptions of mental health among ethnic minorities, there are other reasons that specifically relate to college students' needs. For one, Latinx college students attempt to navigate their family roles while also being a college student. Covarrubias et al. (2019) are one of the few whose research aims to further understand the implications family roles have on first-generation college (FGC) students. After conducting semi-structured interviews, Covarrubias et al. (2019) identified five family roles: providing parental emotional support, acting as a language and finance interpreter, providing physical or financial support, assuming third-parent roles, and being an advice giver. When questioned about their roles, many students shared the pressure and stress their family roles have on them (Covarrubias et al., 2019). Coming from a collectivist background, it is expected that these students play a more active role in their families; however, it appears it is at the expense of their own mental health. Trying to maintain their family roles while being a FGC student actively increases the likelihood of a decline in their mental well-being.

Vasquez-Salgado et al. (2015) focuses on a family versus school mindset, where FGC students feel guilty choosing between their families and academic life. Investigating this specific mindset led the researchers to explore college student's priorities and the conflicts that arise when presented with the option of staying on campus or returning home to their families. Vasquez-Salgado, Greenfield, and Burgos-Cienfuegos (2015) explore these factors after providing scenario-based questions and conducting group interviews with their FGC Latino students. These scenarios included deciding between going home and spending time with their families or staying on campus and focusing on school. Most students responded by trying to

make time for both (Vasquez-Salgado et al., 2015). However, this choice would cause students to rethink if they selected the correct option. Growing up in collectivist culture and upbringing, students learn to work hard for the group and not for themselves. So, based on this study and cultural perspective, students attempted to keep true to collectivism by maintaining their student role and their responsibilities to their family. Consequently, this mentality creates mixed feelings and leads students to spiral within their own guilt.

For students who choose their studies, feelings of guilt surfaced (Vasquez-Salgado et al., 2015). One student shares that their parents would guilt-trip them by sending photos of family or events they did not attend (Vasquez-Salgado et al., 2015). This led the student to feel shame for having chosen their education over family. However, the same feelings emanate even if students choose their families (Vasquez-Salgado et al., 2015). Regardless of their decision, FGC students cannot escape the regret they feel, especially in the context of an American college education. Considering the independence promoted by institutions, this leads to inner turmoil as FGC Latinx students attempt to navigate an entirely new school system while working to meet school and family expectations (Arevalo et al., 2016). As a result, this puts this student population at risk for poor mental health and not completing their degree (Arevalo et al., 2016). Further internalizing this guilt also disrupts the ability to enjoy family time or concentrate on their studies causing their mental health to deteriorate due to their own conflicting emotions.

Reports of family achievement guilt accounts as another contributing factor to lower levels of mental health among FGC students. When analyzing family achievement guilt in relation to family roles, Latinx students scored high on guilt (Covarrubias et al., 2020). These students describe this guilt as feeling mixed emotions for leaving their families behind to further their education (Covarrubias et al., 2020). Tying this all back to collectivism, it's no surprise that

children encounter inner conflict upon leaving their homes (Cite Arevalo). Moreover, because of their collectivist upbringing, students reveal they fear disrupting family harmony (Covarrubias et al., 2015), especially family dependency, resulting in stress. Despite the dramatic increase in future opportunities by attending college, students continue to experience the demands of school life and being an active member in their families.

Additionally, Latinx students can encounter the burden of fulfilling the American Dream on behalf of their parents. Although commonly seen in FGC students, immigrant students can also bear the weight of accomplishing their parent's dreams. In the context of London's (1989) framework of family roles in FGC families, delegation captures the responsibility children feel for working towards their parent's goals (Hartig & Steigerwald, 2007). Consequently, the American Dream becomes an added stressor that students need to navigate as they enter the college education system. Already experiencing the strain of leaving their collectivist homes, students may drown in their own conflicting emotions when debating how to respond.

In light of the extensive research revolving around the Latinx community, very little examines family roles with Covarrubias et al. (2019) being the few to study this. As a result, this thesis will focus on adding to the lack of research by investigating the impact family roles have on Latinx college students' mental health.

Method

After analyzing several pieces of research, one question remains unanswered: how do family roles impact Latinx students' mental health and life as college students? Despite the increase in matriculation of students of color to higher institutions, they continue to face unique challenges along their educational journey. Due to the surge in enrollment rates, it's imperative to understand what stressors Latinx college students encounter and the repercussions it has on their

mental health. Research falls short of highlighting how these responsibilities affect student's mental health. I aim to investigate the effect family roles have on Latinx students' mental well-being during their college years.

Research Aims and Objectives

Bearing in mind the limited research on this topic despite the U.S. being home and refuge to many Latinx individuals, this study ultimately aims to investigate how familial roles impact the mental well-being of Latinx college students in hopes of adding to an understudied area of Latinx literature.

To accomplish this, I will focus on the following objectives:

1. Explore how family roles impact Latinx student's mental health.
2. Identify how to give Latinx students a voice through this research project.
3. Create consent forms that reassure participants of the privacy and de-identification of their data during analysis. This will be especially important to build trust with participants that may identify as undocumented.
4. Under my mentor's guidance, Dr. Harrison, the data will be analyzed in multiple stages; descriptive codes to interpretive analytical codes to thematic codes (Hesse-Biber & Leavy, 2011). It is then my intention to connect the thematic codes to prior research about family roles and mental health detailed in the literature review.
5. Expand on current literature that explores mental health among Latinx college students.

Research Questions and Hypotheses

Furthermore, to fully comprehend the obstacles this student population encounters, the following research questions helped guide this study:

1. What emotional support do Latinx college students provide and receive in their families?

2. What impact do family roles have on being a Latinx college student?
3. How do family roles impact Latinx college students' mental health?

I hypothesize that Latinx college students will provide more emotional support to their families than they receive and that these responsibilities will negatively impact student's mental health. Considering the school versus family mindset that has been investigated, I also hypothesize that Latinx college students will find difficulty in maintaining their family roles during their college years.

Participants

Recruitment of three Psychology students at California State University, Fullerton (CSUF) occurred via the Department of Psychology's Research Pool. This site allows for faculty and students to browse, participate, and publish research opportunities. For this study, I provided basic information such as the study's title, abstract, and eligibility requirements.

To sign-up for an interview, participants must meet the following criteria: (1) be 18 years or older, (2) identify as Latinx, and (3) identify as an immigrant or have immigrant parents/caregivers.

Materials/Apparatus

To collect qualitative and primary data, open-ended questions and a script was created for semi-structured interviews. Both focused on three main topics: family support, family roles and students' mental health pertaining to such roles, and college students' experiences. Said protocol will aid in navigating conversations while allowing for flexibility, follow-up questions, and clarification to occur.

Additionally, electronic consent forms were created for students to sign if they agree to have their interview recorded and shared (emphasis was placed on using a pseudonym or fake name).

Student interviews took place over Zoom, a video meeting computer application, after participants consented to audio recordings. Transcriptions of these conversations simultaneously occurred with the use of Otter.ai, a real-time AI transcript software, to help collect qualitative data. Furthermore, once data analysis of scripts began, Microsoft Excel, a spreadsheet software program, helped to organize common and unique themes found across all participants.

For safe-storing, Dropbox was utilized to save and share interview transcripts between researchers. To ensure confidentiality and limit access, the folder was password protected. When reviewing the consent form, digital signatures and verbal confirmation from participants was needed before commencing interviews. Additionally, within the consent forms and on Research Pool, a note about confidentiality using de-identification and storing of data using a password protected folder in Dropbox was included to provide reassurance on protecting students' privacy.

All computer programs used in this study operated on macOS Ventura 13.2.1.

Procedure

Following IRB approval, the research information became available on CSUF's Research Pool to recruit participants. Given the Psychology Department's five-hour research participation requirement, students can receive course credit at their professor's discretion. With each sign-up, a Zoom link was provided.

During interview sessions, I asked for consent for recordings, sharing of transcripts, and publishing of collected data. Afterwards, semi-structured conversations following a series of questions (demographics, family support, family roles, mental health, and college experiences)

took place. Due to the script touching on sensitive topics, the interviewer will have a similar background to the participants like Covarrubias et al. (2019) did with their interviews. Having an interviewer with a similar background can help build trust on top of reassuring the students on how their responses will be stored and kept confidential.

As previously mentioned, I relied on Otter.ai to draft transcripts of each interview. Discussions with each participant varied in length, but all approximately lasted for about one hour. After the three interviews, transcripts and recordings were revised to fill in missing information and correct for audio-typing mistakes.

Demographics

Integrating demographic questions (race/ethnicity, gender, grade year, and major) into the interview protocol will provide insight into each student's identity. These responses will become the foundation for examining how a student's background influences their family roles.

Moreover, this will provide an added measure of assurance that the students meet the needed requirements of this study before proceeding with the interview questions.

Family Roles

Considering the various family roles an individual can take on, this study defines such responsibilities as specific duties Latinx college students assume to help meet family needs and maintain family dynamics (Epstein et al., 1993). Particularly, I aim to explore how the demands of each family role affects family harmony, especially the impact this has during college years.

Incorporating family role questions will help comprehend what roles Latinx students hold and the effect it has on themselves and their family.

Familial Upbringing

Familial upbringing refers to how adult family members or caregivers raised their children. This could extend to children's role in their family and cultural expectations for each gender or child. Regardless, special attention will be given to student's role in their family, including the cultural expectations for each child depending on their gender.

Culture

Culture will be defined as “a way of life of a group of people— [the behaviors, beliefs, and values that they accept generally without thinking about them]” (Smedley & Smedley, 2005). Emphasis will be placed on the behaviors and values within the culture concerning family upbringing. For example, behaviors of needing to suppress emotions and values of putting family first can potentially be explored.

Mental Health

As for mental health, this research will borrow from Galderisi et al. (2015) proposed definition: how well students can respond to different life stressors and emotions regarding maintaining their family responsibilities, such as their family role, and life balance as a college student. The terms *mental health* and *mental well-being* will be used interchangeably throughout this study.

Enquiring about the participants' mental health allows for an in-depth awareness of how family roles and providing and receiving emotional support from Latinx families impact college student's mental well-being.

Coding Procedure

Descriptive codes and thematic codes (Hesse-Biber & Leavy, 2011) were assigned to qualitative information. To draw overarching and common themes among all participants, script

analysis first occurred by re-reading student conversations and highlighting key points. These main ideas varied depending on the question, but overall stuck to looking for responses that pertained to (1) family roles, (2) emotional support received and given, (3) family roles impact, and (4) any unexpected findings.

Results and Discussion

Family Roles

Across all three interviews, five family roles were identified: providing financial support, acting as a third-parent, language broker, advice giver, and a mediator. All three Latinx students reported providing financial support, while two participants reported taking on the third-parental role, and one student acted as an advice giver, language broker, and assumed the mediator role. Although one student did voice that their older sibling assumed the third-parental role by acting as a parent for them, this role was not included because the student did not take on the responsibility. The three participants names have been changed to maintain confidentiality.

Providing Financial Support

This was one of the most common family roles students reported and described as their parents expecting them to provide monetary support. For instance, both Esmeralda (a female Latinx immigrant college student) and Janix (a female Latinx college student) clearly expressed an expectation of receiving their parent's financial support for college. Janix, however, also expressed feeling concerned about being unable to give back to her parents or meet their expectations of helping provide future financial support with the career path she wants to pursue. On the other hand, Jose (a male Latinx college student) did not have this same expectation of his parents. This is how he described his financial contribution to his family.

“...I didn't really have much in terms of monetary needs, so I had to work at the swap meet starting at the age of 8 up until college. As I was not well off, I do not take anything I currently have for granted.”

Jose shared his family's low income and the necessity to begin working from a young age to help provide for his family. He expressed how his background and upbringing influenced his outlook on finances and values.

Future expectation for children to provide financial support

Although this study focuses on current family roles relating to students' mental health and college experience, two participants shared that there has been the added expectation of providing future financial support to their families ever since they started college.

With Janix, she reveals the financial hardship her family has experienced over the past years. She articulates that her parents work hard, get little sleep, and earn little to nothing. Because she's witnessed her parents trying to make ends meet, she expresses her ambition to succeed and give back to her parents. But, Janix realized that to do so, she had to give up on her first dream of becoming a fashion designer. She claims that pursuing this career is a gamble and states that: “[we] have to be successful and make it big in the future for the sake of our parents. Hence, we don't have the time, effort, or money for taking on risks.” Here, Janix describes what collectivism looks like for her: where she chose a career that will allow her to provide for her family instead of pursuing one that she likes. Even though providing future financial support is an expectation that Janix took on herself, this future responsibility affected her mental well-being and time in college. Her the internalized collectivism motivates her to work towards a degree that helps accomplish her goal of being able to help her family financially.

Esmeralda's story differs from Janix's in that the former believes her role has changed in the sense of having more expectations of what future family roles she will play to support her family

because of her college education. She says “My family role has definitely changed in regards to having more expectations on the depth of the role I will one day play in supporting my family as they see college as guaranteeing I’ll be financially secure.” The student speculates her family's expectations have increased, specifically in providing financial support, because her parents have recognized her potential and capabilities by letting her take on more roles during college.

Esmeralda struggles to balance her family-school life. However, because her parents do not see this, they assume she is managing her responsibilities well, which can explain why her family expects more of her.

Third-Parental Role

Assuming the role of the “third-parent” is commonly seen among older Latinx siblings. Covarrubias et al. (2019) notes that their student population reported responsibility over their siblings’ health, transportation, and other aspects of their lives. Adding to this, Esmeralda revealed that her role encapsulates responsibilities outside the home like “...filling out documents for school to guiding [her younger siblings] through school in their pursuit of eventually applying to college.”

On the other hand, Janix summarizes her role through at-home tasks like reminding her brother “[what he needs to get done], by what time, and remind [him] how my mom likes things to be done.”

When recalling her family’s financial hardships, Janix also mentions that her role reached its peak during this time as she “took care of [her] younger brother as much as [she] could.” So, regardless of what each student’s duties are, both highlight their influence over their younger siblings and their active role in their lives apart from just being their sister.

Advice Giver

Acting as an adviser is another common family role, but only one student reported taking on this role. Esmeralda said “In regards to my sisters, I play the role of being the older sibling who provides advice and guidance in their lives using my own experiences.” Here, she discusses that she gives advice to her younger siblings because she is much older than them and has accumulated more knowledge and life experiences, leading her sisters to come to her when they need guidance. This could potentially stem from Esmeralda taking on the third-parental role since her siblings see her as someone they can rely on when they need support or help navigating certain life events. But, this role also extends to Esmeralda’s mom, who seeks her help when difficulties arise with her sisters. Esmeralda recalls one instance in which her mom needs extra support, especially “...when it comes to understanding topics like mental health [regarding her sisters.]”

Providing details of the times she’s acted as an advice giver, it appears Esmeralda plays an essential role in guiding her sisters and mom in times of need.

Language Broker

Despite previous Latinx literature reporting 38.24% FGC students identifying as a language broker for their families, where they wrote checks and filled out paperwork (Covarrubias et al., 2019), only one student reported assuming this role in this study. Esmeralda explains her responsibility as “...[playing] the role of being someone who they can rely on for things like helping them fill out paperwork in English.” This explanation reflects Esmeralda's parents' reliance on her to fill out documents since they do not speak English. However, even though only one student revealed taking on this specific role, the tasks align with Covarrubias et al.'s (2019) student participants discussion of how these tasks take time out of their day to assist their parents due to the language barrier.

Mediator Role

For the most part, the family roles the students described remain consistent with previous literature. However, one new family role was the mediator role, where one student reported resolving any family conflict. This particular role is unique to this study because previous literature does not discuss this responsibility.

Esmeralda hints at this role when asked, “*how important do you feel your family role is in maintaining your family structure*”? She says, “I also am the one...who helps mediate between the family when any conflicts or problems occur.”

Given this description, Esmeralda takes on the extra duty to dissipate and resolve family conflict. It appears that this family responsibility could also be connected to how the “mediator role” helps provide emotional support to the family.

Emotional Supports Given and Received

This section explores the emotional support students give to their families, specifically how their family roles help provide this extra aid and the emotional support students receive in return.

Emotional Support Given

After identifying the types of family roles, it seems like Latinx college students give more emotional support than they receive from their families. Among the three participants, the two female students took on the most roles (with the immigrant student taking on more between the two), while the male student carried out one role (providing financial support) during his time in college. For instance, Esmeralda, the immigrant student, is responsible for fulfilling all five family roles (providing financial support, third-parental role, act as an advice giver, language broker, and as a mediator), with Janix assuming two (providing financial support and assuming

third-parental roles). Both students express their attempts to maintain family roles as they pursue higher education (which will be further discussed).

Jose is a peculiar case where his primary responsibility is providing financial support. But, he refrained from sharing what emotional support looks like within his family, so I was unable to determine if he gives or receives any help.

Emotional Supports Received

From the interviews, Esmeralda appears to have received emotional support from their family. She reflects on her parent's initial lack of awareness of mental health since she states that her parents didn't know how to provide this support or the importance of mental health. This statement remains consistent with previous literature where parents describe psychological or mental health issues as physical problems (De Silva et al., 2020). However, this same participant reported that their parents are more aware of mental health now but, despite her parents gaining a new perspective on mental health, she continues to feel like she cannot reach out to them for help because she's ashamed for complaining about her responsibilities as a college student and someone their family relies on.

With this, my first hypothesis (that Latinx college students provide more emotional support from their families than they receive) was supported since Esmeralda, Janix, and Jose took on more family roles and shouldered the responsibility of carrying out her family and college life duties at once. To further understand the depth of these roles, these home responsibilities were analyzed in relation to student's time in college and their mental health.

Family Roles Impact

Considering the reported family roles and emotional support by Latinx college students, family roles appear to impact them in unexpected ways, such as the expectations their families

have for them to excel in school while continuing to carry out their home responsibilities. Additionally, students expressed the influence pursuing higher education has had on their parent's future anticipation of them helping the family. Lastly, students discuss the impact their family roles have had on their mental health as college students.

Current Expectations

With the number of family roles identified earlier, only two students comment on current family expectations. Both participants reflect on the pressure to excel in school, while carrying out their home responsibilities. For example, Janix reveals that her family expects too much from her causing her to take on more than she can handle. For Esmeralda, she remarks that she presumes her family expects her to be someone reliable that can juggle several responsibilities at once, like maintaining the third-parental role and pursuing higher education.

Additionally, Esmeralda chimes in that her parents also expect her to prioritize being with her family to be with family or help them with anything that comes up. She reports that she has neglected her own mental health recently because:

“...she also has all these roles she had to play at home like helping her parents organize her sister's quince which literally consumed her entire spring break which was supposed to be time for her to catch up on school work and make sure she's okay mentally.”

With this, it appears that these students' families expect more from them as college students. Particularly, their families seem to care more about their daughters finding their own balance between all their duties, while overlooking the pressure and effect it has on their mental well-being. It could also be the parents of FGC students are genuinely unaware of the experiences and stressors their children face given that they did not attend college. Wang (2014) study on the messages FGC students receive from their parents supports that parents might be

more concerned with affirming their presence to their children (e.g., don't forget about us, your family will always be there for you, you don't have to worry).

College Experiences, Family Roles, and Mental Health

Given the number of family roles identified thus far, it appears to take a toll on two students' mental health. Esmeralda and Janix reported stress, anxiety, and guilt as they attempted to navigate their family-school life balance. This theme remains consistent with previous literature in finding difficulty maintaining family-school life balance. One student recalled the times when she failed to prioritize her studies over her family. Esmeralda describes the guilt-tripping she experienced when her parents would respond negatively to her decision to stay at school and focus on studying for exams instead of spending time with her family. She says:

“There were many times where I didn't properly study for exams or didn't put as much effort as I should have into school because my parents expected me home or else they'd say I didn't want to spend time with them.”

This family versus school conflict is the same strife Vasquez-Salgado et al. (2015) explores with their student participants. Their students reported the same guilt of choosing between returning home or concentrating on schoolwork (Vasquez-Salgado et al., 2015). Esmeralda depicts the same internal struggle as she gives in and goes home because she "had to go home and be there for [her] sisters or help [her] parents with something."

Not only that, but Janix also expressed the same sentiments by not having the time for school, meet her family responsibilities, and for herself. She said, “I have so much to do as a student and daughter, but sometimes I'm told to just drop everything and alter my schedule to fit my family's.”

These findings aren't surprising, considering that Latinx culture emphasizes collectivism. As explored earlier, collectivism is ingrained within Latinx culture, causing Latinx college

students to encounter stress, guilt, and anxiety when they realize they don't have the time to accomplish everything they need to. In other words, it's difficult for them to decide how to divide their time while still maintaining their family roles as college students.

Remarkably, Jose reported that his current role is to earn his college degree. This is unique because studies have yet to explore this perspective as a male. But there is research that proposes Latino men grew to value their independence during their higher education due to gender socialization experiences (Rodriguez et al., 2021). Plus, the role of earning his degree could also have been influenced by the behavioral traits that Jose learned when he was younger in that he needs to become a leader, a provider, and responsible. So, instead of feeling the same shame and regret other Latinx college students encounter, like Esmeralda and Janix, Jose finds comfort in that:

...college has [given him the distance to dissociate from his roles]...[and given him a way to get out of the toxic family dynamic he was part of]...[and given him the time he needed to heal from that].

Jose says he does not hold any current family roles because college has given him a way out of his previous responsibilities. He even goes as far as to point out that his four years at school have allowed him to heal from past stress and worries. As a result, his mental well-being recovered compared to when he lived with his parents and later on with just his father.

Originally, I hypothesized that assuming these family roles would negatively impact Latinx college students' mental health, especially if they give more emotional support than they receive from their families. As a result, my hypothesis was partially supported because two students reported the pressure they felt attempting to maintain their family and school responsibilities. However, the third student expressed how his time at college has allowed him to dissociate and heal from his family dynamics. Similarly, my hypothesis that Latinx college

students would struggle to maintain their family roles was also partially supported. Because two students addressed the lack of time and difficulty in navigating home-school life, this reinforces my initial prediction, but since the last student, once again, conveyed the autonomy they gained since starting college from no longer feeling tied down to their home responsibilities, this partially supports my hypothesis. Aside from these findings, immigration status unexpectedly appears to significantly influence family roles and their effect on students' mental health and college experience.

Unexpected Findings: Immigration Status Impact

Unforeseen and unaccounted for, immigration status seems to play a role in the family roles Latinx college students assume. Plus, imposter syndrome was reported by an immigrant student as a contributing factor to affecting her mental health, on top of experiencing the pressure to maintain her family roles as a Latinx college student. These findings will be further discussed below.

Immigration Status Influence on Family Roles

Considering the five family roles reported by the three participants, it appears that immigration status greatly influences students' responsibilities. For instance, Esmeralda and her parents are immigrants, and she bears the most roles out of the three students. Specifically, she takes on all five roles, briefly summarized earlier. During the interview, she acknowledged the impact immigration status has had on her duties to maintain her family structure:

“Being aware that both my parents and I are immigrants has definitely put pressure on our roles in the sense that I think we all feel obligated to work harder and feel more inclined to strive for more to make all the sacrifices of immigrating to another country worth it.”

Here, Esmeralda describes the stress she experiences to ensure she is putting all her efforts into guaranteeing future success due to her and her family's immigrant status. The cultural

disconnect she mentions could also explain why she feels obligated to take on so much within her family. She discloses that:

“...when it comes to certain cultural differences and understanding why my parents may see things differently than my siblings and I do as their own background influenced them to see things...in a drastically different way than we were taught to view it in American society.”

This cultural clash can indicate the complexity that coexists between immigration status and the cultural rift that could potentially influence the number of responsibilities Latinx college students take on.

Despite Janix assuming the least number of family roles, she recounts how her mom's immigration status and family's financial hardships at the time impacted her to assume the third-parental role. She reflects how “[she tried her best to be independent and take care of her younger brother as much as she could].” Even though Janix is not an immigrant, her mom's immigration status and her family's situation influenced her to become independent and take responsibility for helping care for her younger sibling since “[they didn't have a mom or dad to rely on].”

Again, both student responses capture the effect immigration status has on the family roles they take on. Even though one student is an immigrant, while the other isn't, they both experience the significant impact immigration status has on their roles in helping maintain family dynamics.

Racism, Discrimination, and Imposter Syndrome

Unexpectedly, one student shared their experience as a student immigrant, which has caused her to feel insecure about her accomplishments. Recounting her college acceptances, Esmeralda mentions:

“...there was a student who even said that I only got in because I was brown which haunts me to this day as I have moments where I question why I am where I am and question whether I deserve it compared to students I know also deserve the space. These insecurities definitely have kept me back from...opportunities at times.”

The racism and discrimination recounted, highlights the inferiority and insecurity Esmeralda internalized as an immigrant Latinx student. Furthermore, she continues to describe the lack of confidence she often feels due to both her and her parent's immigration status by noting that:

“[she also recognizes her immigration status and her parents' immigration status has formed a sense of inferiority and insecurity that takes root in some parts of herself that prevent her from having the same confidence that pushes other students into opening up and taking up spaces in academia or even reaching out to people asking if they have opportunities for her.]”

However, despite the prejudice targeted against her for identifying as Latinx, her imposter syndrome is mediated by using her immigration status and her parents' support as motivation to strive for more. She explains this by saying she uses all available resources to pursue her goals.

This part of the interview captures the complexity of being an immigrant Latinx college student. For one, it triggers self-doubt and insignificance due to encounters with racism and discrimination from peers, which adds to inner turmoil as one navigates a predominately white education system. Consequently, this reduces one's mental health; yet the report of using one's immigration status as determination to achieve their goals proves how immigration status can serve as a double-edged sword. While it can bring despair, it can also evoke optimism and hope that they, too, can succeed as students of color. As a result, immigration status is likely to influence Latinx college students' roles and impact their mental health as they pursue higher education.

Future Directions and Limitations

Given this study's major limitation of having three student participants, I advise increasing the sample size and recruiting Latinx students from various institutions and majors to gain more perspectives on family roles and the challenges of balancing their student and family responsibilities. One area that can provide new insight into family roles is to add socioeconomic status as a reported demographic. Considering that all of the students in my study reported providing or are expected to provide future financial support, this could be due to their family's current financial status. So, by exploring socioeconomic status, future work can determine if the number and type of family roles change among social class. Furthermore, gender can also be investigated in future studies. In this project, two students identified as female and one as male. Despite these three students taking on different roles with some overlapping, the female students expressed having more pressure and anxiety versus the male student, who felt more liberated after starting college. Studying gender differences can help identify if gender influences what family roles each gender assumes within the Latinx community. Plus, this area of research can determine if gender impacts family expectations and obligations.

Conclusion

This study aimed to identify what emotional support they give and receive in their families, how these roles affect their mental health, and the effect it has during their time as college students. After coding my qualitative data, I found that Latinx college students provide more emotional support to their families than they receive. Not only that, but I also discovered that some students felt guilt as they tried to maintain their family roles, causing a strain on their mental health, with one student reveling in finally dissociating from these home responsibilities,

which improved his mental well-being. Lastly, I determined that two students found difficulty navigating their family-school life while one enjoyed the independence of college.

This study adds to an underrepresented area of Latinx literature, specifically on how family roles impact Latinx college students' mental health. The main limitation of this study was the small sample size. I recommend recruiting more participants from various institutions and backgrounds for future research. Future studies can explore gender differences to determine if gender influences family roles and expectations.

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